

PCM SOLAR AIR HEAT EXCHANGER AND ITS VENTILATION PREHEATING EFFECTIVENESS

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ABSTRACT

This article presents a PCM solar air heat exchanger integrated into ventilated window developed to maximize the use of the solar energy to pre-heat the ventilated air. The system is designed to improve the indoor air quality and thermal comfort by continuous pre-heated air supply at a reduced energy use through the capturing and storing of solar energy. This study examines the thermodynamic behavior of the system both experimentally and numerically. This entails a full-scale experiment in climate boxes to study the thermal storage and heat release ability of the facility. Accordingly, a numerical model combining heat transfer and buoyancy derived laminar flow and nonlinear thermal properties of the PCM is built and validated with the experimental data. The model is then used for configuration optimization of the PCM solar air heat exchanger to maximize the solar energy storage and the ventilation pre-heating effectiveness. The results show that for a 6-h solar charging period, the optimum PCM plate depth is 90 mm and the optimum air gap thickness is 6 mm. The same configuration can be used for both summer night cooling and winter solar energy storage applications. The total stored/released latent heat after one charging period is 93.31 MJ/m³.

Keywords:

Municipal Solid Waste, Biological Treatment, Thermal Treatment, Physical Treatment

INTRODUCTION

Building energy use for ventilation and HVAC systems amount to more than one-third of the total energy use in industrial countries and about 40% of the total energy use in Europe, and it shows growing trends as a result of increased thermal comfort requirements and climate changes. It has become a burden to the environment and the fossil fuel resources. To diminish the fuel consumption and carbon dioxide emission caused by building energy use, it is necessary to implement innovative technical solutions and renewable energy resources in the built environment. Many researchers have studied renewable energy such as solar energy applied in building energy systems to reduce the traditional building energy use. Excess renewable energy is often stored in thermal energy storage (TES) facilities with the advantages of grid peak shifting, building energy conservation, and the building thermal mass level improvement. Phase change material (PCM) applied in TES is one of the most promising solutions for renewable energy storage and has recently drawn much attention within the scientific community. Unlike the materials with only sensible energy storage, PCM releases/absorbs large amounts of latent heat during its phase transition in a small temperature range. The heat capacity of PCM during the phase transition period is much higher than the conventional building materials. The high energy density of the PCM offers a large heat storage ability with a relatively small storage volume, which makes it a good candidate for TES. With adequate design and choices, the phase transition of the material occurs within the range of indoor thermal comfort, which allows direct applications of PCM in the building environment [2]-[4]. ventilative heating or cooling systems integrating PCM for thermal storage is a common building application, which

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several research groups have tested and studied. For example, ventilation night cooling during a warm summer discharges PCM units at nighttime (cold storage) and then utilize these units during daytime to cool down the hot outdoor air used as ventilation inlet air. Some other strategies focus more on power load peak shaving and demand shifting. For instance, Labatt et al. designed a PCM-to-air heat exchanger storage for heating, ventilation, air conditioning (HVAC) systems to shift the cooling demand from high to low electricity price periods. The PCM is discharged (cooled down) by the HVAC systems during low electricity price periods. The discharged PCM is then used during high price periods to decrease the energy demand for cooling. In winter time, PCM can be used directly or indirectly with solar energy systems or as TES integrated with other heating systems such as heat pump, floor heating, and ceiling heating. Studies have shown that the integration of PCM in the building environment can significantly increase the building heat storage capacity and, thereby, improve the indoor space heating energy flexibility and ease the building demand-side management. De Garcia et al. tested a ventilated double skin facade with PCM in the air cavity for both cooling and heating purposes. They found out that such PCM ventilation system can effectively prevent overheating in summer and reduce the electrical consumption of the HVAC system in winter[5]-[7].

Solar collectors can be used for providing pre-heated air to ventilation systems. The traditional solar air collector consists of an absorber and a transparent glass, and it facilitates airflow inside the collector. Applications for solar collectors can be found in drying systems for agriculture and marine products, packed bed thermal storage unit, as well as space heating systems. Nevertheless, a large heat transfer area and high flow rates are required for good performances because of the low thermal capacity and thermal conductivity of the air and the low convection coefficient on the surface of the absorber[8]. Applying PCM to the solar-air collector system has the advantage of more thermal energy storage, longer thermal release time, and more stable pre-heated air temperature. However, the conventional method to apply PCM into a solar collector system is to use the material as the heat storage medium in the storage tank. The heat transfer fluid between the solar collector and the PCM heat storage tank is usually water. The PCM in this system always has a relatively high phase change temperature (around 40–60 °C)[9].

This paper proposes a different solution to apply PCM into the building energy system. It includes a double glazing ventilated window and a PCM heat exchanger. The system is designed to improve the indoor air quality and thermal comfort by continuous pre-heated air supply at a reduced energy use through the capturing and storing of solar energy. The double glazing window works as a trombe wall during the daytime when solar radiation is available. The PCM solar air heat exchanger directly stores the heat from the solar radiation and releases the heat later when solar radiation is less available to pre-heat the ventilated air. It has a smaller volume compare to the conventional PCM tank. The PCM in the solar-air heat exchanger has a phase change temperature around room temperature, which is good for the indoor thermal comfort. The relatively thin PCM plates compensate for the low thermal conductivity of the PCM and make the heat store and release processes faster[10].

LITERATURE SURVEY & REVIEW

Akash Kumar Modi[1], This review paper is based on theories and complications related to air-preheater & the heat transfer surfaces used in it. Numerous papers and sufficient amount of literature were gone through to understand how an airpreheater is designed and the performance parameters associated with the same. Air-preheaters (APH) are heat exchangers, which are used to pre-heat the air before any other process takes place. APH finds its wide use in power plants, automobiles and all such areas where there is a need to pre-heat the air and save fuel. A thorough survey was also done on the heating elements or surfaces used in air-preheaters for the transfer of heat between cold and hot fluid. Various types of widely used profiles were identified first and a research was then conducted to find out how the experimental investigation of heat transfer plates can be done. Excerpts have also been provided regarding the design of experimental setup for the same and the dependence of various parameters on one another. The paper is concluded with an opinion on the use of plate profiles for air-preheater.

Stephen K[2], Heat exchangers as a heat transfer device has gained wide applications across different levels of domestic and industrial set-ups. Various studies have been carried out to study, analyse and predict its performance. However, one major phenomenon that limits heat exchanger performance is attributed to fouling. Based on this, various studies and approaches have focused on reduction, elimination and mitigation of fouling. This study therefore focused

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on this. It reviewed several attempts that have been carried out to understand and mitigate the incidents of fouling in heat exchangers. The study found that despite the existing models developed towards understanding fouling, there is no single model that has provided an accurate prediction of fouling in all the different types of heat exchangers. Also, majority of existing results have limited applications and some of the solutions are only peculiar to particular type of heat exchanger. Further to this, majority of the study results only pointed to small scale laboratory test schemes and there is absence of in-situ measurements that predicts actual (real life) service performance.

RuiGuo el at[3], This article presents a PCM solar air heat exchanger integrated into ventilated window developed to maximize the use of the solar energy to pre-heat the ventilated air. The system is designed to improve the indoor air quality and thermal comfort by continuous pre-heated air supply at a reduced energy use through the capturing and storing of solar energy. This study examines the thermodynamic behavior of the system both experimentally and numerically. This entails a full-scale experiment in climate boxes to study the thermal storage and heat release ability of the facility. Accordingly, a numerical model combining heat transfer and buoyancy derived laminar flow and nonlinear thermal properties of the PCM is built and validated with the experimental data. The model is then used for configuration optimization of the PCM solar air heat exchanger to maximize the solar energy storage and the ventilation pre-heating effectiveness. The results show that for a 6-h solar charging period, the optimum PCM plate depth is 90 mm and the optimum air gap thickness is 6 mm. The same configuration can be used for both summer night cooling and winter solar energy storage applications.

Aditya Chauhanel at[4], This chapter presents a detailed overview on the use of phase change materials (PCMs) for being used in various building applications particularly from the viewpoint of reducing fossil fuel-based energy consumption in the buildings for HVAC (heating, ventilation, and air conditioning) and other applications. Buildings form the major portion (30%) of the total energy consumption worldwide; thus there exists an ample opportunity to exploit the latent heat of PCMs for thermal regulation in buildings. Also the growing concerns over environmental issues which are directly linked with the emission of greenhouse gases through building air conditioners have made us to rethink and critically examine the alternate and sustainable techniques as per the building's requirement. Use of phase change materials particularly in the last decade has gained a significant attention from all round the globe not only from research point of view, but its use now has also become commercially viable for various thermal energy storage-based building applications. The chapter follows a comprehensive approach, i.e., starting from the introductory concepts like sensible and latent heat, classification of phase change materials, and selection criteria for PCMs to the most advance techniques like microencapsulation adapted for various building applications which have been discussed in sufficient detail. The large amount of stored latent heat and the peculiar isothermal nature of heat addition and rejection during phase change have made phase change materials (PCMs) an ideal candidate for storage-based thermal regulation in buildings. Special attention has been given to PCM's use in building applications categorized as (i) water and air heating applications, (ii) HVAC/solar absorption systems for building, (iii) building integrated systems (walls, ceilings, and floors), and (iv) other useful techniques like Trombe wall, PCM shutters, and PCM concrete.

WenyeLin[5], Thermal energy storage (TES) using phase change materials (PCMs) has received increasing attention since the last decades, due to its great potential for energy savings and energy management in the building sector. As one of the main categories of organic PCMs, paraffin's exhibit favorable phase change temperatures for solar thermal energy storage. Its application is therefore effective to overcome the intermittent problem of solar energy utilization, thereby reducing the power consumption of heating, ventilation and air conditioning (HVAC) systems and domestic hot water (DHW) systems. This chapter reviews the development and performance evaluation of solar thermal energy storage using paraffin-based PCMs in the built environment. Two case studies of solar-assisted radiant heating and desiccant cooling systems with integrated paraffin-based PCM TES were also presented. The results showed that paraffin-based PCM TES systems can rationalize the utilization of solar thermal energy for air conditioning while maintaining a comfortable indoor environment.

These of TES system is essential for solar power systems because of fluctuations in the solar energy input. Several classes of storage may be required for a single installation, depending on the type and scale of the solar power plant

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itself and the nature of its integration with conventional utility systems. For heating and hot water applications, water and PCMs constitute the principle storage media. Soil, rock another solids are used as well. Some PCMs are viscous and corrosive and must be segregated within the container in order to be used as a heat transfer medium [6].

Since solar radiation is an inherently time-dependent energy resource, storage of energy is essential if solar is to meet energy needs at night or during daytime periods of cloud cover and make a significant contribution to total energy needs. Since radiant energy can be converted into a variety of forms and feasible to be stored such as; thermal energy, chemical energy, kinetic energy, or potential energy. Generally, the choice of the storage media is related to the end use of the energy and the process employed to meet this application. The optimum capacity of the storage device for a given solar process depends on the time dependence of the solar availability, the nature of the load, the cost of auxiliary energy, and the price of the process components. These factors must all be weighed carefully for a particular application to arrive at the system design (including storage size), which minimizes the final cost of delivering energy [7].

Storage of solar energy is important for the future success of solar energy utilization. The major problem is the selection of materials having suitable thermo physical characteristics in which solar energy in the form of heat can be stored [8]. The materials can be divided into two broad types (Figure 1): those that store energy in the form of sensible heat and those that undergo a change of state or physical-chemical change at some temperature within the practical range of temperature provided by the solar heat collectors as likely 90 to 120°F[9].

If we talk about the thermal heat storages purposely for solar thermal applications, then (i) SHS: as sensible heat in solids (e.g., rocks, or liquids such as water). The heat storage medium thereby experiences an increase in temperature without undergoing a change in its phase, (ii) LHS: as latent heat of fusion in suitable chemical compounds (e.g., paraffin waxes and inorganic salts). The heat storage medium absorbs the heat added and undergoes a phase transition from the solid to the liquid state at a desired temperature within the operating temperature range [10].

PROPOSED SYSTEM

A. presents the configuration of the ventilated window with the PCM solar air heat exchanger. The ventilated window is a double glazing window with an air cavity between the two glazing layers, which allows ventilated air to go through. The solar air heat exchanger is made of parallel PCM plates separated by thin air gaps. The PCM plates are mounted in a wood frame with a glass on the front surface. There are openings on the top and bottom of the PCM heat exchanger frame and on the top of the ventilated window, to enable the ventilation of air through the system.

*Fig. 1. Description of the ventilated window with PCM heat exchanger .
(a) Front view; (b) Side view.*

The system is designed to improve the indoor air quality and thermal comfort by continuous pre-heated air supply at a reduced energy use through the capturing and storing of solar energy. Fig. 2 illustrates the operation strategy of the ventilated window system in winter or transition seasons. In the daytime, the system is in solar energy storage mode (see Fig. 2(a)). The solar radiation charges the PCM in the solar air heat exchanger when solar energy is available. The ventilation air only passes the ventilated window and is heated up by the solar radiation, before it enters the indoor room. The ventilation pre-heating mode is on when the solar radiation is less than 200 W/m^2 , as seen in Fig. 2(b). The cold ambient air passes the solar air heat exchanger from the bottom, and the stored heat heats it up. Then the pre-heated air passes through the double glazing window into the indoor space. The ventilation bypass mode is on when there is a cooling need in the space, and the inlet air temperature from the window system should be close to the outdoor air temperature, and at a maximum the airflow rate, as seen in Fig. 2(c).

Fig. 2. System operation strategy (a) solar energy storage mode; (b) ventilation pre-heating mode; (c) ventilation bypass mode.

With the new solar air heat exchanger ventilation system, solar energy and the PCM solar storage preheat the ventilation air to make the most use of the solar energy and to increase the inlet air temperature and thermal comfort in winter. It can benefit both the buildings under renovation and the new buildings. In building renovation, the install an efficient ventilation system with heat recovery is a challenging work. The application of the presented system can be an alternative method to ensure an energy efficient ventilation solution in these buildings. Moreover, the installation of the application only requires some façade envelope reconstruct. The easy installation of the system makes it good for the building renovation projects. For new buildings with decentralized ventilation solutions, the system can contribute to improve the energy efficiency of the buildings by better capture and utilization of the solar energy. The solar energy added into the building energy system is used to cover the heat demand of the buildings. As a result, the building energy consumption is reduced.

Tools / Platform

CAD (Computer Aided Design) is the use of computer software to design and document a product's design process. Engineering drawing entails the use of graphical symbols such as points, lines, curves, planes and shapes. Essentially, it gives detailed description about any component in a graphical form.

Background

Engineering drawings have been in use for more than 2000 years. However, the use of orthographic projections was formally introduced by the French mathematician Gaspard Monge in the eighteenth century.

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Since visual objects transcend languages, engineering drawings have evolved and become popular over the years. While earlier engineering drawings were handmade, studies have shown that engineering designs are quite complicated. A solution to many engineering problems requires a combination of organization, analysis, problem solving principles and a graphical representation of the problem. Objects in engineering are represented by a technical drawing (also called as drafting) that represents designs and specifications of the physical object and data relationships. Since a technical drawing is precise and communicates all information of the object clearly, it has to be precise. This is where CAD comes to the fore.

EXPERIMENT AND RESULT

The heat storage and heat release processes of the solar air heat exchanger are tested with a full-scale experiment in a *Hot Box* and *Cold Box* setup in the laboratory, as shown in Fig. 3. Both of the boxes are equipped with cooling coil and electric heater. The air temperature in the cold box is controlled by proportional integral derivative (PID) controllers at 8 ± 1 °C. A ventilation system connects the two boxes and creates an under-pressure in the hot box compared to the cold box by operation of a fan in the ventilation duct. It induces an air flow from the cold box to the hot box through the solar heat exchanger. The air flow rate during the ventilation pre-heating mode is kept constant at $106 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$, which is measured by the orifice plate.

In this section, the optimized results of the depth of the PCM plates and the thickness of the air gap are presented. All the cases have an air flow rate set at $106 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$. 5 cases with different plate depths are studied first. The air gap thickness is kept at 6 mm, the same as in the experimental setup. The aim of using the PCM solar air heat exchanger for ventilation preheating is to save heating energy use mainly in winter and transition seasons. The optimization is based on the energy saving potential of the PCM heat exchanger exposed to 550 W solar charging for 6 h, which is equal to the average daily radiation received in April in Denmark. Fig. 4 shows the temperature at the vertical section in the middle of the PCM plates at time 6 h. A 550 W evenly distributed heat flow is applied to each of the PCM plates from the right side. From the temperature contours shown in Fig. 4, it can be observed that the PCM melt in the top right side of the PCM plate. The right side of the PCM starts melting first. The heat is transferred into the left side of the plate by the conduction in the PCM plates and the convection in the air gaps between the PCM plates. The area of the PCM plate with a temperature lower than 23 °C decreases with the decrease of plate depth, which indicates a higher melting fraction for a smaller PCM plate depth. However, the total volume of the PCM is decreasing with the decreasing of the PCM plate depth. Therefore, there exists an optimum PCM plate depth to maximum both the PCM melt fraction and the PCM volume in the system. The PCM at the bottom of the plate has a lower temperature because of the shelter of the inlet of the PCM heat exchanger, which prevented sunlight to reach this part. The PCM temperature is highest in the upper right corner, because of the heat flow direction and convection in the air gap between the PCM plates.

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Fig. 3. Experimental setup of the solar air heat exchanger test.

Fig. 4. Vertical PCM temperature profile in the middle of the plates after 6 h charging for different plate depths.

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CONCLUSION

The ventilation air only passes through the ventilated window to be pre-heated by solar radiation. When the solar radiation is lower than 200 W/m^2 , the ventilation air passes through the PCM solar collector, where the PCM heat storage preheats it, and then the air is supplied to the room to make the most use of the captured solar energy to increase the air inlet temperature and thermal comfort in winter. In building renovation, it can be challenging to install an efficient ventilation system with heat recovery and the application of the presented system can be an alternative method to ensure an energy efficient ventilation solution in these buildings. Also, for new buildings with decentralized ventilation solutions, the system can contribute to improve the energy efficiency of the buildings by better capture and utilization of the solar energy.

This work presents a full-scale experimental test to evaluate the thermal behaviour of the solar air heat exchanger. Accordingly, a numerical model with conjunct heat transfer and buoyancy driven laminar flow is built. The simulation results are in good agreement with the experimental data. Configuration optimization is conducted with different plate depths and different air gap thicknesses for a PCM heat exchanger in both the solar energy storage and the ventilation pre-heating modes. For a 6-h solar charging period, the optimum PCM plate depth is 90 mm and the optimum air gap thickness is 6 mm. The same configuration can be used for both summer night cooling and winter solar energy storage applications. The total stored and released latent heat during one charge is 93.31 MJ/m^3 .

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